

Investigating the Relationship between Religious Beliefs, Epistemological Beliefs, and Moral Justice with Academic Performance the Mediating Role of Students' Social Adaptation

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The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between religious beliefs, epistemological beliefs, and moral justice with academic performance as a mediator of social adaptation in Payam Noor University students. This research was descriptive in terms of applied purpose and method and structural equation correlation. The statistical population of this study consists of all students of the Payam Noor University of Tehran in 1398. The sample of the study was 384 students who were selected by available sampling. Research data were collected using the Questionnaire of Religious Beliefs of Khodadadi Far et al., Birger Moral Justice, Schumer Epistemological Beliefs, and California Social Adaptation. Validity of the scales used second-order factor analysis with AMOS software and Cronbach's alpha was used for reliability. Descriptive statistics and Pearson correlation coefficient and structural equation test were used to analyze the data and answer the research hypothesis. Findings showed that religious beliefs, moral justice, and epistemological beliefs have a positive and significant effect on the social adjustment and academic performance of students. The results of structural equation modeling showed that 52% of the variance of social adjustment and 62% of students' academic performance is explained by religious beliefs, moral justice, and epistemological beliefs. Recognizing the factors affecting students' social adjustment and academic performance provides the possibility of forecasting and planning to help ensure their mental health and can be done by creating a suitable religious context in universities to increase students' academic performance and clarify the type of thinking. Students pay at the university.

Religiosity. moral justice. epistemological beliefs. academic performance. social adaptation